

DOMINION UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

**HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
(A CASE STUDY OF ACTION MEDICAL CENTER.)**

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award of Bsc. Computer Science with Management.**

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DECLARATION

Candidate's Declaration

I hereby declare that this Long Essay is the result of my own original research and that no part of it has been presented for another degree in this university or elsewhere.

Candidate's Signature:..... Date:.....

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Supervisor's Declaration

I hereby declare that the preparation and presentation of the Long Essay was supervised in accordance with guidelines on supervision of dissertation laid down By Dominion University College.

Supervisor's Signature:..... Date:.....

Name: **MR. JERRY YAO DEKU**

ABSTRACT

Hospitals currently use a manual system for the management and maintenance of critical information. The current system requires numerous forms, with data stores though out the hospital management infrastructure. Often information (on forms) is incomplete, or does not follow management standards. Forms are often lost in transit between departments requiring a comprehensive auditing process to ensure that no vital information is lost. Multiple copies of the same information exist in the hospital and may lead to inconsistencies in data in various data stores.

A significant part of the operation of any hospital involves the acquisition, management and timely retrieval of great volumes of information and medical history, staff information, room and ward scheduling, staff scheduling, operation theatre scheduling and various facilities waiting lists.

All of this information must be managed in an efficient and cost wise fashion so that an institution's resources may be effectively utilised HMS will automate the management of the hospital making it more efficient and error free. It aims at standardizing data, consolidating data integrity and reducing inconsistencies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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I also wish to thank workers of Action medical centre ; my research would not have been impossible without their valued

Contributions

My deepest gratitude goes to my families for their unflagging love and support throughout my life; this research is simply impossible without them.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this project to God Almighty, and my families.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

IT- Information Technology

IS- Information System

ICT- Information and Communication Technology

UML-Uniform Modelling Language

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Hospitals deal with the life and health of their patients. Good health care relies on well-trained doctors and nurses and on high quality facilities and equipment. Good medical care also relies on good record keeping. Without accurate, comprehensive and up to date and accessible patient notes, medical personnel may not offer the best treatment or may in fact misdiagnose the condition., which can have serious consequences.

Associated records, such X-rays, specimens, drug records and patient registers, must also be well cared for if the patient is to be protected. Good records care also ensures the hospitals administration runs smoothly; unneeded records are transferred or destroyed regularly, keeping storage areas clear and accessible; key and records can be found quickly, saving time and resources. Records also provide evidence of the hospital's accountability for its actions and they form a key source of data for medical research, statistical reports and health information systems.

Managing Hospital Records addresses the specific issues involved in managing clinical and non-clinical hospital records. A comprehensive records management system in a hospital helps to ensure that staff have access both to clinical information and to administrative records on a wide range of issues, including policies, precedents, legal rights and obligation, personnel, finance, buildings, equipment and resources.

Records Management refers to an on-going process of managing the records in a media neutral basis in accordance with approved policies, procedures and schedules. Records Management as a discipline defines and applies business rules related to the creation, protection, retrieval and disposition of an organization as records over time. Retention schedules are the cornerstone of a successful Records Management process.

Statement of Problem

After careful investigation of the current method of rendering medical and allied services to the patients of action medical centre following problems were discovered: Non-integration of all parties involved in service delivery. There is delay in attending to patients, In-accurate record keeping and information redundancy.

Purpose of the Study

Customer satisfaction is an important measure of firm performance because of its positive influence on customer loyalty (Anderson, 1997)

Previous research has documented that increased customer loyalty secures future revenues, reduces the cost of future transactions, decreases price elasticity and minimizes the likelihood of customer defection in the event of poor quality of service.

Therefore, this study seeks to access the effect of information technology investments on patient service delivery.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked:

1. What are the IT-based services offered by AMC?
2. Has the introduction of IT investment significantly affected service delivery at AMC?
3. Has IT positively affected service delivery in AMC?
4. Has IT services significantly changed customer's perception about AMC?
5. Given the usage of IT services, how satisfied are customers of the CLINIC?

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this project work is to design an efficient web-based system for the advancement of medical research and analysis, which will make it easy to follow up a patient's Medical records from any workstation in the hospital. This would thus replace method of one point entry and retrieval that exist in non-web-based system. The work would also help in

Speeding up the processing, storing and retrieval of information which would greatly assist medical personnel in performing their duties.

It will also help to improve decision making by reducing processing time as well as reducing the communication gap between the doctor and other staff still involved in the patient medical care. It would also help to reduce human errors to the barest minimum and improving confidentiality of file.

General Objectives

The general objective of the study is to add to the general body of knowledge and Research area on the effect of information technology investment on customer service delivery and to determine the challenges faced by the patients of AMC with regards to I.T.

Specific Objectives

The specific objective of this project will be:

- a. To examine and analyse the existing system
- b. To develop a web based hospital management system that is suitable for hospitals.
- c. Implementation of the system

Significance of the Study

In the area of health delivery, Hospitals can benefit a lot from the use and the supportive roles That web-based system will enhance.

1. Stock inventory management/ administration
2. Patient's administration
3. Drug administration
4. Staff administration/ management

As a result, when all this are established they will in turn provide crucial information for proper management of the system

Delimitation

As a result of resource limitation in both time and money, this study is based on patient's management, secure access of user and hierarchy of information and integration of all users into the health care delivery process.

Limitation of Study

A lot of setbacks were encountered in course of this project. There were constraints in many areas like:

1. Finance: The high cost of materials for the project and everyday constraint increase transportation tax during data collection affected research work
2. Data Collection: The research work had a problem in collecting data from staff. However, I still remain indebted to the staff who generously contributed immensely making this project have contributed immensely
3. Materials: Materials constrains play a major role in that limiting some research that would have contributed immensely.

Definition of Technical Terms

Some vital terms used for the purpose of carrying out this research are as follows:

Online: online is the condition of been connected to a network of computers or other device.

Authentication: is the act of confirming the truth of an attribute of a datum or entity.

Computer: This is the foremost and important term needed to carry out the research. It an electronic device which operates by taking some raw materials in form of data and converting them into some useful results

Communication: a way of providing a gateway for the interaction of the various components with external applications, through different types of protocols.

Data: this comprises raw facts and figures that are processed into information

Information: output from a system; this has been processed to give it meaning.

Database: this is a collection of structural data. The structure of the data is independent of any particular application.

Record: A group of related field.

Organization of the Rest of the Study

Besides this chapter one, the rest of the study is organized as follows:

Chapter two presents a review of the relevant literature of the study. Chapter three discusses the methodology that was employed in collecting data for the study. It also includes data sources, sample population, size, and selection, and method of data analysis. Chapter four presents the results and interpretation of the findings from the field and chapter five presents a summary, conclusions and recommendations for policy and practice for the study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hospital

A hospital is a health care institution providing patient treatment with specialized staff and equipment. The best-known type of hospital is the general hospital, which has an emergency department. A district hospital is the major health care facility in its region, with large numbers of bed for intensive care and long-term care. Specialised hospitals include trauma centres, rehabilitation hospitals, children's hospitals, seniors (geriatric) hospitals, and hospitals for dealing with specific medical needs such as psychiatric problems (see psychiatric hospital) and certain disease categories. Specialised hospitals can help reduce health care cost compared to general hospitals. A teaching hospital combines assistance to people with teaching to medical students and nurses. The medical facility smaller than a hospital is generally called a clinic. Hospitals have a range of departments (e.g. surgery, and urgent care) and specialist units such as cardiology. Some hospitals have outpatient departments and some have chronic treatment units. Common support units include a pharmacy, pathology and radiology.

Hospitals are usually founded by the public sector, by health organizations (for profit or non-profit), by health insurance companies, or by charities, including direct charitable donations. Historically, hospitals were often founded and funded by religious orders of charitable individuals and leaders. Today, hospitals are largely staffed by professional physicians, surgeons, and nurses, whereas in the past, this work was usually performed by the founding religious orders or by volunteers. However, there are various Catholic religious orders, such as the Alexians and the Bon Secours sisters that still focus on hospital ministry today, as well as several other Christian denominations, including the Methodists and Lutherans, which run hospitals.

In accordance with the original meaning of the word, hospitals were originally “places of hospitality”, and this meaning is still preserved in the names of some institutions such as the Royal hospital Chelsea, established in the 1681 as a retirement and nursing home for veteran soldiers.

Types of Hospital

Some patients go to hospital just for diagnosis, treatment, or therapy and then leave (outpatients) without staying overnight; while others are ‘admitted’ and stay overnight or for several days or weeks or months (“inpatients”). Hospitals usually are distinguished from other medical facilities by their ability to admit and care for inpatients whilst the others often are described as clinics.

1. General

The best-known type of hospital is the general hospital, which is set up to deal with many kinds of disease and injury, and normally has an emergency department to deal with immediate and urgent threats to health. Larger cities may have several hospitals of varying sizes and facilities, some hospitals, especially in the United States and Canada, have their own ambulance service.

2. District

A district hospital typically is the major health care facility in its region, with large number of beds for intensive care and long-term care.

In California, “District hospitals” refers specifically to a class of healthcare facility created shortly after World War 11 to address a shortage of hospital beds in many local communities. Even today, District hospitals are the sole public hospitals in 19 of California’s countries, and are the sole locally-accessible hospital within 9 additional countries in which one or more other hospitals are present at substantial distance from a local community. Twenty-eight of California’s rural hospitals and 20 of its critical-access hospitals are District hospitals.

California’s District Hospitals are formed by local municipalities, have Boards that are individually elected by their local communities, and exist to serve local needs. They are particularly important provider of healthcare to uninsured patients and patients with Medi-Cal (which is California’s Medicaid program, serving low-income persons, some senior citizens, persons and disabilities, children in foster care, and pregnant women). In 2002, District hospitals provided \$54 million in uncompensated care in California.

3. Specialized

Types of specialized hospitals include trauma centres, rehabilitation hospitals, children hospitals, seniors (geriatric) hospitals, and hospitals for dealing with specific medical needs such as psychiatric problems, certain disease categories such as cardiac, oncology, or orthopaedic problems, and so forth. In Germany specialized hospitals are called Fachkrankenhaus: an example Fachkrankenhaus Coswig (thoracic surgery).

A hospital may be a single building or a number of buildings on a campus. Many pre-twentieth-century origins began as one building and evolved into campuses. Some hospitals are affiliated with universities for medical research and the training of medical personnel such as nurses, often called teaching hospitals.

Worldwide, most hospitals are run on a non-profit basis by government or charities. There are however a few exceptions, e.g. China, where government funding only constitutes 10% of income of hospitals.

Specialised hospitals can help reduce healthcare cost compared to general hospitals. For example, Narayana Hrudayalaya's Bangalore cardiac unit, which is specialised in the cardiac surgery, allows for significantly greater number of patients. It has 3000 beds (more than 20 times the average American hospital) and in paediatric heart surgery alone, it performs 3000 heart operations annually, making it by far the largest such facility in the world. Surgeons are paid on a fixed salary instead of per operation, thus the costs to the hospital drops when the number of procedures increases, taking advantage of economies of scale. Additionally, it is argued that costs go down as its entire specialist become efficient by working on one "production line" procedure.

4. Teaching

A teaching hospital combines assistance to people with teaching to medical students and nurses and often is linked to a medical school, nursing school or university. In some countries like UK exists the clinical attachment system that is defined as a period of time when a doctor is attached to a named supervisor in a clinical unit, with the broad aims of observing clinical unit, with the broad aims of observing clinical practice in the UK and role of doctors and other healthcare professionals in the National Health Service (NHS).

5. Clinics

The medical facility smaller than a hospital generally called a clinics, and often is run by a government agency for health services or a private partnership of physicians (in nations where private practise is allowed). Clinics generally provide only outpatient services.

Department or Wards in Hospitals

Hospitals consist of departments, traditionally called *wards*, especially when they have beds for inpatients, when they are sometimes also called *inpatient wards*. Hospitals may have acute services such as an emergency department or specialist trauma centre, burn unit, surgery, or urgent care. These may then be backed up by more specialist units such as the following:

1. Emergency department
2. Cardiology
3. Intensive care unit
 - Paediatric intensive care unit
 - Neonatal intensive care unit
 - Cardiovascular intensive care unit
4. Neurology
5. Oncology
6. Obstetrics and gynaecology, colloquially, maternity ward.

In addition, there is the department of nursing, often headed by a nursing officer or director of nursing. This department is responsible for the administration of professional nursing practice, research, and policy for the hospital. Nursing permeates every part of a hospital. Many units or wards have both a nursing and a medical director that serve as administrators for their respective disciplines within that specialty, in an intensive care nursing, the director of neonatology is responsible for the medical staff and medical care while the nursing manager/director for the intensive care nursery is responsible for all of the nurses and nursing care in that unit/ward.

Some hospitals have outpatient departments and some have chronic treatment units such as behavioural health services, dentistry, dermatology, psychiatric ward, rehabilitation services, and physical therapy.

Common supports units include a dispensary or pharmacy, pathology, and radiology. On the non-medical side, there often are medical records departments, release of information departments, information management (aka IM, IT or IS), clinical engineering (aka biomed), facilities management, plant ops (operations, also known as maintenance), dining services, and security departments.

Architecture

Modern hospital buildings are designed to minimise the effort of medical personnel and the possibility of contamination while maximising the efficiency of the whole system. Travel time for personnel within the hospital and transportation of patients between units is facilitated and minimised. The building also should be built to accommodate heavy departments such as radiology and operating rooms while space for special wiring, plumbing, and waste disposal must be allowed for in the design.

However, the reality is that many hospitals, even those considered ‘modern’, are the product of continual and often badly managed growth over decades or even centuries, with utilitarian new sections added on as needs and finances dictate. As a result, Dutch architectural historian Cor Wagenaar has called many hospitals.

“...built catastrophes, anonymous institutional complexes run by vast bureaucracies, and totally unfit for the purpose they have been designed for....They is hardly ever functional, and instead of making patients feel at home, they produce stress and anxiety.”

Some newer hospitals now try to re-establish design that takes the patient’s psychological needs into account, such as providing more fresh air, better views and more pleasant colour schemes. These ideas harken back to the late eighteenth century, when the concepts of providing fresh air and access to the healing power of nature’ were first employed by hospital architects in improving their buildings.

The research of BRITISH Medical Association is showing that good hospital design can reduce patient’s recovery time. Exposure to daylight is effective in reducing depression. Single sex accommodation help ensure that patients are treated in privacy and with dignity. Exposure to nature and hospital gardens is also important – looking out windows improves patient’s moods and reduces blood pressure and stress level. Eliminating long corridors can reduce nurse’s fatigue and stress.

Another on-going major development is the change from a ward-based system (where patients are accommodated in communal rooms, separated movable partitions) to individual one in which they are accommodated in individual rooms. The ward-based system has been described as very efficient, especially for the medical staff, but is considered to more stressful for patients with their own rooms is however found in the higher cost of building and operating such a hospital; this cause some hospitals to charge for the private rooms.

Brief Historical Overview

The process used to collect, process, and store patient information to aid clinical treatment are probably as old as medicine. The formats for collection of patients' records and the ways in which this information is used and subsequently stored for future references has continued to evolve from regular paper note takings to electronic taped records and present-day hospital information technologies. Wilke (2008) defined information literacy that affects medical practice as the ability to identify the need for information and seek, evaluate, and use information in any presented format. Information technology infusion that aids globalization refers to the degree to which various information technology tools integrate into organizational activities (Idowu et al., 2006)

The growth of computer technology in the 1980s with consequent improvement in information literacy saw the advent of the first breed of hospital information systems (Keena et al., 2006). Earlier researchers in hospital information systems categorized them into three types: Consumer informatics, medical and clinical informatics, and bio informatics based on areas of application (Detmer, 2001).

Consumer informatics focuses on communications between patients and the public. According to Svensson (2002), consumer informatics helps to create virtual communities for sharing of health care information.

Medical and clinical informatics applications relate directly to health care organizational processes, structure, and clinical outcomes. Electronic medical records system is a major medical and clinical information system aimed at the lowering cost of health care therapies (Svensson, 2002).

In its earliest applications, hospital information systems were mostly used for patient's electronic record keeping, but have advanced into almost all areas of medical discipline. Common applications of hospital information systems, Laboratory information systems, Radiology information system and picture Archival and Communication Systems, Telemedicine, and many others as these technologies are constantly evolving.

William and Boren (2008) acknowledge that most European countries and United State are increasingly adopting electronic medical record (EMR) technology to enhance health care outcome and quality. William and Boren posited that Ghana lacks robust health care infrastructures and policies for implementation of information and communications technology (ICT). Complicated by challenges of epidemics and civil wars, African countries lack ICT in their health care systems. The authors asserted that historically, lack of human expertise and inadequate financial resources is a bane to robust to adoption of ICT in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Benefits of Hospital Information Systems

Hospital Information System improves workflow and increase patient's access to health care (Ouma & Herselman, 2008; et al., 2006; Wallis 2007). Sisniega (2009) asserted that the applications of information and communications technologies facilitate ubiquitous and instantaneous communication between organizations and their stakeholders. ICT enable people and organizations to achieve seamless workflow and effective through improved interactions. Electronic health technologies enable effective networking by physicians; allow online review of patient's treatment, and providing for accurate prescription of drugs. Radiology systems enable the transmission of radiological images for evaluation in remote sites (Weimar, 2009).

Electronic data exchange is part of the applications of a robust and integrated electronic health records system. The type of integrated system envisioned by President Bush's administration is aimed at warehousing the health care information of all Americans in a national database by 2004 (Theist, 2007)

Electronic data interchange primarily is aimed at achieving continuity of care, irrespective of patient migration from one clinician to another or from one city to another.

A study on electronic medical records by Keenan et al. (2006) found improvement in daily work and enhanced patient care: (a) medication turn-around times fell from 5:28 hours to 1:51 hours; (b) radiology procedure completion times fell from 7:37 hours to 4:21 hours; and (c) lab results reporting times fell from 31:3 minutes to 23:4 minutes. In the same study, transcribing errors for orders declined, and length of hospital stay decreased. Other benefits of electronic medical records systems are possibility for online monitoring of vital signs, capability for multi-site review of patient's records, and improved physician's collaboration in patient care. EMR facilitates easy access to medication administration records, sharing of consultation reports, and decreased transmit time of test results by reducing the time taken to deliver paper versions (Keenan et al., 2006).

In a heterogeneous society like Ghana with significant disparity in accessibility of health care facilities between urban and rural communities, hospital information systems may help to bridge the gap in availability of patient care (Ouma & Herselman, 2008). Sammon, et al. (2006) associated patient data analysis systems (PDAs) with enhanced storage and analysis of patient data enabling physicians to reach improved and clinical decisions on patient care. Similarly, clinical information systems capture clinical data to enhance prompt and efficient decision making (Ward et al., 2006; William & Boren 2008). Health care policy makers seeking ways of improving quality of patient care at a reduced cost are leveraging hospital information systems to achieve these objectives (Sammon et al., 2008; Simon et al., 2008).

A major challenge that exists for health care systems is the integration of software systems that can service the various needs of the organization. Stone, Patrick, and Brown (2005) opined that effective organization creates specific and strategic objectives, including objectives related to the clinical and operational strategies (p. 33). Failing to address the interrelationships that exist between the strategies can result in unforeseen negative consequences (p.34). In the implementation of an electronic medical record, an organization that fails to identify the need for the EMR system to communicate or integrate with the billing software may likely encounter increase process failures requiring additional resources for correction. Successful organizations develop strategies capable of identifying organizational needs. Such organizations anticipate challenges and launch remediation efforts by installation of computer networks and systems (Stone et al., 2005). A positive correlation is found between adoption of health care information technology and positive organizational financial performance in general and operational performance by health care providers using novel information systems (Menachemi, Burkhardt, Shewchuk, Burke, & Brooks, 2006). In the industry, electronic commerce transactions have enabled banking and the retail industry to lower cost of services and improved ease of access to products for their customers by using the Internet (Sisniega, 2009).

Attributes of superior organizational performance in health care include improved quality of care and patient safety.

Morath and Turnbull (2005) recommended creating a culture of safety in health care organizations by recognizing and accommodating the multiple complexities of those organizations. A laudable approach would be to take advantage of the ability of large-scale data systems to amass information as means of identifying significant trends, and enable creation of blame-free sanctuaries in which care errors and observations of incompetence receive prompt solutions. Data production and collection requires knowledge to facilitate this untaken. Various forms of knowledge are essential business asset used for development of new products and services, thereby useful in developing a competitive advantage in the marketplace (Rennolls & AL-Shawabkeh, 2008).

Cohan (2005) expressed a contrary view that investment in information technology does not necessarily transcend to improvement in productivity. Cohan stressed that shortfall in productivity expectations have made industrial leaders more cautious in adopting information technology in their organization processes. Presenting a balanced view, Farquharson (2009) asserted that adoption of information technology increases productivity but falls short of expectation in improvement of productivity considering the high capital investment required for implementation. Farquharson surmised that industry productivity paradox exists to some extent with implementation of ICT. Furukawa, Raghu, Spaulding, and Vinze (2006) argue that hospital information systems enhance quality of health care delivery and safety.

Medical errors in diagnoses and drug administration decline with applications of electronic health systems. Electronic physician order entry and medication reconciliation helps patients to understand better, the beneficial effect of drugs and deleterious effects of drug misuse (Kramer et al., 2007). Fuji and Galt (2008) opined that more than 1.5 million United State residents suffer injuries from prescription errors and other medical errors annually. Citing the 2008 Institute of Medicine report, *to Err is Human*, the authors suggested that the above figure might represent only a fraction of patient's exposed to adverse medical errors when patient's own mix-up is taken into account. Fuji and Galt surmised that some elements of hospital information systems increase patient participation in care process, thereby reducing unwanted outcome of treatment. Laboratory information systems (LIS) have evolved within the last decade (& McDowell, 2008). Harrison and McDowell (2008) linked the evolution of LIS technology to advancements in information technology solutions, stressing that LIS has led to an increased awareness in the development of technological solutions designed to minimize medical errors. Following the publication of the Institute of Medicine's report in the early 2000s and the Institute for healthcare improvement's saving 100K Lives Campaign; industry awareness has increased on the need for solutions to minimize medical errors (Harrison & McDowell, 2008).

The LIS industry has accepted the challenge and developed innovative software solutions that include patient result verification, the recognition of critical values in the addition to the immediate transfer of critical values to physicians for evaluation, and enhanced turnaround time (Harrison & McDowell, 2008).

Interfacing software is available is available to merge the laboratory information operating systems with electronic health record (HER) systems, enhancing the continuum of communication among providers.

Stone, et al. (2005) and Harrison and McDowell anticipated the future of LIS and EHE will provide increased patient safety, enhance quality of care, and a leaner operating system resulting in efficient and productive processes. Woodside (2007) concur that health care organizations use electronic data interchange to share patient histories, treatment plans, lab results, and insurance information. Sharing the patient's history in an exchange facilitates initiation of care and decreases the chances of errors. Data interchanges that involve physician's orders and pharmacies can protect patients by detecting prescriptions of incompatible drug combinations, and highlighting potential allergens to patients. Another vital function of the electronic interchange is the verification of insurance benefits. Many providers do not run tests, ship supplies, or provide care without assurance that the patient's has insurance coverage and that the insurance company has authorized the expenditure's. Electronic interchange between entities helps avoid delays in the approval process and decrease the possibility of poor outcome because of a delay in treatment. Information technology in general enables intra organizational networking that facilitates effective information flow within the various units of a firm. In the world of an organization's complex networking, workforce diversity, and departmentalization, information can become lost in a milieu of activities; hence, decision-making, schedule of responsibilities, and an information flow chart are necessary for effective organizational operations (Hargie & Dickson, 2007).

In addition to prompt delivery of investigation reports to patient's and clinicians, some aspects of information technology enable decisions made on organizational processes to be

timely and effectively dissemination to the workforce. Analytical software systems provide means for both dissemination of information and relevant quantitative data to support management decisions. Analytical information systems help organizations to maintain a competitive edge in the marketplace by increasing operational speed and maintaining fluidity of information flow (Azevado, Ferraira, & Leitao, 2008). Crane and Crane (2006) reported that numerous solutions for the medication error problem in hospital settings might be averted with the use of an integrated systems approach. However, execution of an organization's integrated electronic medical record without use of communication billing software may escalate process breakdowns. Philips (2009) stated that the use of an integrated system electronic medical record without use of communication billing software may escalate process breakdowns. Philips (2009) stated that the use of an integrated system offers considerable conceptual flexibility and data interaction capabilities instead of using one module for electronic records. An integrated records system promotes a user-interface with e-records repository to facilitate storage and eventual retrieval of records.

Other benefits of electronic health systems include optimizing of clinical time because of effective communication and increased compliance with regulatory guidelines (Georgiu, Westbrook, Braithwaitem, & Iedema, 2005). Keenan et al (2016) opined that electronics medical records system provide an effective educational tool for training of resident doctors and medical students. Health care information technology and e-health offer strong potential in research and development of clinical protocols. Future studies on this area may provide broader implications of health care information technologies application (Keenan et al., 2006)

The new among health care organizations in a changing global environment is the adoption of sophisticated information systems to support clinical operations and strategic management. Major attributes of current systems include an emphasis on information protection, provision and disease management software, and programs that reduce medical errors. Future trends will seek to improve interoperability, expand the use of the internet, and development of electronic health (e-health) applications. More vendors are likely to focus on smart devices with wireless capabilities to improve data entry and retrieval and support consumers through development of niche home appliances (Glandon et al., 2008). Electronic Health Records (EHR), smart cards, and fraudulent use of information by others,

According to Garets and Horowitz (2008), clinicians should engage in evaluation of hospital information technologies because information systems will become repositories of clinical data. Electronic medical records system and other information systems will attain commonplace applications in hospitals and other health care centres in the coming decade. President Bush set a target of developing electronic health records for all Americans by 2014 (Theist, 2007). Health care policy makers and organizational leaders should work to understand the operational intricacies of various hospital information technology options in readiness for universal adoption in the next few years (Garet & Horowitz, 2008).

The future trend in Ghana is hard to predict. The demand for adoption of innovative technology abounds, but the economic implications and other infrastructural requirements put a barrier to adoption.

The Ghanaian government and governments of their African countries will have to invest heavily on information to facilitate any attempt aimed at catching up with the developed world in the adoption of hospital information technologies (Ouma & Herselman, 2008)

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter discusses the methodology used, the research setting and the methods used for data collection. This essentially described the general approaches to the study and how the data were analyzed. This chapter of project work is dedicated to the system analysis and design of the hospital management system

Research Design

The Hospital management System will be implemented using a distributed architecture with a database server for the information storage, a middleware application and a client side application. The client side will be designed using HTML (Hyper Text Markup Language) and will be viewed with a web browser. The records and information about the hospital will be stored using My SQL online database server while the middleware application will be implemented using PHP server side scripting language

Unified Modelling Language

The Unified Modelling Language (UML) is a general-purpose modelling language in the field of software engineering, which is designed to provide a standard way to visualize the design of a system

In 1997 it was adopted as a standard by the Object Management Group (OMG), and has been managed by this organization ever since. In 2005 the Unified Modelling Language was also published by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) as an approved ISO standard. Since then it has been periodically revised to cover the latest version of UML

System Block Diagram for Hospital Management System

Figure 4.1

Use Case Diagram

A use case diagram at its simplest is a representation of a user's interaction with the system that shows the relationship between the user and the different use cases in which the user is involved.

A use case diagram can identify the different types of users of a system and the different use cases and will often be accompanied by other types of diagrams as well.

Use Case of Hospital Management System

SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

Sequence diagram and collaboration diagram are called INTERACTION DIAGRAMS. An interaction Diagram shows an interaction, consisting of set of objects and their relationships including the messages that may be dispatched among them.

Figure 4.3

Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modelling Language, activity diagrams are intended to model both computational and organizational process (i.e. workflows). Activity diagrams show the overall flow of control.

Activity diagrams are constructed from a limited number of shapes, connected with arrows. The most important shapes types:

- i) Rounded rectangular represent action;
- ii) Diamonds represent decisions;
- iii) Bars represent the start (split) or end (join) of concurrent activities
- iv) A black circle represents the starts (initial state) of workflow;
- v) An encircled black circle represents the end (final state)

Hospital Management System

Activity Diagram

Figure 4.4

DATABASE DESIGN

The database design will be used to design the hospital management system as shown below using MySQL.

Patients Table Database Structure

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra	Action
1	patient_id	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT	Change Drop Primary Unique More
2	patient_code	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
3	patient_title	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
4	patient_first_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
5	patient_last_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
6	patient_middle_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
7	patient_gender	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
8	patient_civil_status	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
9	patient_age	int(3)			No	None		Change Drop Primary Unique More
10	patient_birth_place	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
11	patient_phone	varchar(13)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
12	patient_email	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
13	patient_house_no	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
14	patient_drop_code	tinyint(1)			No	None		Change Drop Primary Unique More
15	patient_date	datetime			Yes	CURRENT_TIMESTAMP		Change Drop Primary Unique More
16	patient_city	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More

Table 4.1

Employee Table Database structure

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra	Action
1	employee_id	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT	Change Drop Primary Unique More
2	employee_id_badge	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
3	employee_first_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
4	employee_last_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
5	employee_email	varchar(60)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
6	employee_phone	varchar(13)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
7	employee_position	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique More
8	employee_drop_code	tinyint(1)			No	None		Change Drop Primary Unique More
9	employee_created_on	datetime			Yes	CURRENT_TIMESTAMP		Change Drop Primary Unique More

Table 4.2

Department Table Database structure

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra	Action
1	department_id	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT	Change Drop Primary Unique Index Spatial Fulltext More
2	department_name	varchar(45)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique Index Spatial Fulltext More

Table 4.3

Room Table Database structure

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra	Action
1	room_id	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT	Change Drop Primary Unique Index Spatial Fulltext More
2	room_name	varchar(100)			Yes	NULL		Change Drop Primary Unique Index Spatial Fulltext More
3	room_code	tinyint(1)			No	None		Change Drop Primary Unique Index Spatial Fulltext More

Table 4.4

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

The clinical Management Information System was implemented using various development tools like:

- i. HTML for implementing the web server
- ii. PHP to implement the MIDDLEWARE
- iii. My sql for storing the data

System implementation follows the approval of the system proposals and its objectives, so as to arrive at a satisfactory, implemented, completed, and evaluated function of the Hospital Management System.

Implemented Plan

The new system will be implemented along side with the old system with a view to strengthening the inadequacies of the old system; hence a parallel approach plan will be used to implement the system.

System Implementation

Shown and described below are the various stages that were encountered during the implantation of the proposed system.

Login Form: The form is used to allow the users access to the system by providing their authentication details

Figure 4.5

Admin Form: This form allow and admin staff to add employee, delete employee, update employee, ad schedule, update schedule and to edit password.

The image shows a screenshot of a web application interface for a hospital management system. A modal window titled '+ Add New Employee' is open, displaying a form to complete the details of a new employee. The form includes a circular profile picture placeholder on the left and several text input fields on the right: Employee ID#, First Name, Last Name, Email, Position, and Phone Number. At the bottom right of the modal, there are two buttons: 'Close' (red) and 'Save' (teal). The background shows a dashboard with a search bar for employees and a table with columns for 'Created On' and 'Action'. The user is logged in as 'Admin User'.

Figure 4.6

Receptionist Form: This form allows the receptionist to manage patient's registration and patient appointment

The image shows a web application interface for patient management. A modal window titled '+ Add New Patient' is open, displaying a form for entering patient details. The form is organized into two main sections: 'Personal Information' and 'Contact Information'. The 'Personal Information' section contains eight input fields: a dropdown for title, text boxes for first, last, and middle names, a text box for age, a dropdown for gender, and text boxes for birth place and civil status. The 'Contact Information' section contains four input fields: text boxes for phone number and email, and text boxes for 'Where you Live?' and house number. At the bottom right of the modal, there are two buttons: a red 'Close' button and a teal 'Save' button. The background shows a blurred view of the main application dashboard with a search bar and a table of patient records.

Figure 4.7

System Maintenance

In a matter of time, the usage, the requirement of the individual may change, therefore, equipment installation and implementation of a working system is not the end of the system analysis and design, there is need for maintenance to ensure that the system continually meets the objectives or achieved its specific goals

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Introduction

This chapter makes conclusions and suggests policy recommendations.

Conclusions

The project **Hospital Management System (HMS)** is for computerizing the working in a hospital. It is a great improvement over the manual system. The computerization of the system has speed up the process. In the current system, the front office managing is very slow. The hospital managing system was thoroughly checked and tested with dummy data and thus is found to be very reliable. The software takes care of all the requirements of an average hospital and is capable of providing easy and effective storage information related to patients that come up to the hospital.

It generates test reports and also provides the facility for searching the details of the patient. It also provides billing facility on the basic of patient's status whether it is an indoor or outdoor patient. The system also provides the facility of backup as per the requirement.

RECOMMENDATION

Training of all members of staff of the hospital is to be of high priority, this being a new system, some members of the staff may be threatened that the computerized Hospital management system will replace their job. I would also recommend that management of the hospital should make available an avenue to train and educate the staff regularly. It also recommended that the hospital should be providing adequate facilities for the implementation and also hopes that they will strive to improve on this system.

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APPENDIX

HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.

(A case study of Action Medical Centre)

I am final year student of Dominion University College pursuing a degree in Computer science with Management. We are researching on the above topic.

Part A

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `bed`;
```

```
CREATE TABLE `bed` (
```

```
  `bed_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
```

```
  `roomid` int(11) NOT NULL,
```

```
  `bed_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
```

```
  `bed_count` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,
```

```
  `roomtypeid` int(11) NOT NULL,
```

```
  PRIMARY KEY (`bed_id`)
```

```
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;
```

```
LOCK TABLES `bed` WRITE;
```

```
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `bill`;  
  
CREATE TABLE `bill` (  
  `bill_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,  
  `bill_service` text,  
  `bill_amount` decimal(13,2) DEFAULT NULL,  
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,  
  `pat_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,  
  `drop_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`bill_id`)  
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;  
  
LOCK TABLES `bill` WRITE;  
  
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `complain`;

CREATE TABLE `complain` (
  `complain_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `complain_details` text,
  `complain_remarks` text,
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`complain_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--

-- Dumping data for table `complain`

--

LOCK TABLES `complain` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `department`;  
  
CREATE TABLE `department` (  
  `department_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,  
  `department_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`department_id`)  
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;  
  
--  
  
-- Dumping data for table `department`  
  
--  
  
LOCK TABLES `department` WRITE;  
  
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `diagnosis`;

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client = @@character_set_client */;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = utf8 */;

CREATE TABLE `diagnosis` (
  `diagnosis_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `diagnosis_details` text,
  `diagnosis_remarks` text,
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`diagnosis_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `diagnosis`
--

LOCK TABLES `diagnosis` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `discharge`;

CREATE TABLE `discharge` (
  `discharge_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `admission_reason` text,
  `discharge_condition` text,
  `final_diagnosis` text,
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`discharge_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--
-- Dumping data for table `discharge`
--

LOCK TABLES `discharge` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `employee`;

CREATE TABLE `employee` (

  `employee_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

  `employee_id_badge` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_first_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_last_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_email` varchar(60) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_phone` varchar(13) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_position` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `employee_drop_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  `employee_created_on` datetime DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,

  PRIMARY KEY (`employee_id`)

) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

--

-- Dumping data for table `employee`

--

LOCK TABLES `employee` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `ipd`;

CREATE TABLE `ipd` (
  `ipd_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `pat_id` int(11) NOT NULL,
  `doc_id` int(11) DEFAULT NULL,
  `ipd_status` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `ipd_discharge` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,
  `ipd_confirm` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,
  `ipd_date_time` datetime DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,
  `deptm_id` int(11) NOT NULL,
  `ipd_date` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `ipd_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `patn_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `ipdbed_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`ipd_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

-- Dumping data for table `ipd`

LOCK TABLES `ipd` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `medication`;

CREATE TABLE `medication` (
  `medication_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `drug_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `days` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `quantity` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `instruction` text,
  `advice` text,
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`medication_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

--

-- Dumping data for table `medication`

--

LOCK TABLES `medication` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `opd`;

CREATE TABLE `opd` (

  `opd_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

  `pat_id` int(11) NOT NULL,

  `doctor_id` int(11) NOT NULL,

  `opd_status` varchar(20) DEFAULT NULL,

  `opd_discharge` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  `opd_confirm` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  `opd_date_time` datetime DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,

  `opd_date` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `dept_id` int(11) NOT NULL,

  `opd_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `pat_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  PRIMARY KEY (`opd_id`)

) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

-- Dumping data for table `opd`

LOCK TABLES `opd` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `operation`;

CREATE TABLE `operation` (

  `operation_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

  `from` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `to` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `operation_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,

  `diagnosis` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,

  `doctor_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,

  `assistants` text,

  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  PRIMARY KEY (`operation_id`)

) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

--

-- Dumping data for table `operation`

--

LOCK TABLES `operation` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `patient`;

CREATE TABLE `patient` (

  `patient_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

  `patient_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_title` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_first_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_last_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_middle_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_gender` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_civil_status` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_age` int(3) NOT NULL,

  `patient_birth_place` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_phone` varchar(13) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_email` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_house_no` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `patient_drop_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  `patient_date` datetime DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,

  `patient_city` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
```

```
PRIMARY KEY (`patient_id`)  
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;  
  
-- Dumping data for table `patient`  
  
LOCK TABLES `patient` WRITE;  
  
UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `progress`;

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client = @@character_set_client */;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = utf8 */;

CREATE TABLE `progress` (
  `progress_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `date_time` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `progress_name` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  `treatment` text,
  `remarks` text,
  `op_code` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,
  `prepared_by` varchar(255) DEFAULT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`progress_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

-- Dumping data for table `progress`

LOCK TABLES `progress` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;

```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `room`;

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client = @@character_set_client */;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = utf8 */;

CREATE TABLE `room` (
  `room_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `room_name` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
  `room_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`room_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = @saved_cs_client */;

--

-- Dumping data for table `room`

--

LOCK TABLES `room` WRITE;

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `roomtype`;

/*!40101 SET @saved_cs_client = @@character_set_client */;

/*!40101 SET character_set_client = utf8 */;

CREATE TABLE `roomtype` (
  `roomtype_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,
  `roomtype_name` varchar(100) DEFAULT NULL,
  `roomtype_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY (`roomtype_id`)
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=4 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

-- Dumping data for table `roomtype`

LOCK TABLES `roomtype` WRITE;

INSERT INTO `roomtype` VALUES (1,'General Ward',0),(2,'Executive Suite',0),(3,'deluxe',0);

UNLOCK TABLES;
```

```

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS `users`;

CREATE TABLE `users` (

  `user_id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,

  `first_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `last_name` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `access_level` varchar(45) DEFAULT NULL,

  `password` varchar(128) DEFAULT NULL,

  `email` varchar(60) DEFAULT NULL,

  `drop_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  `created_on` datetime DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,

  `confirm_code` tinyint(1) NOT NULL,

  PRIMARY KEY (`user_id`)

) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=10 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;

-- Dumping data for table `users`

LOCK TABLES `users` WRITE;

INSERT INTO `users` VALUES
(1,'Admin','User','Admin','25f9e794323b453885f5181f1b624d0b','admin@hms.com',0,'2017-03-
16 12:40:05',0);

UNLOCK TABLES;

```